

Sodium-Manganese Oxides in Faradaic Desalination: Achieving Long-Cycling Stability Through Morphological and Structural Optimization

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Water scarcity, driven by climate change and population growth, necessitates innovative desalination technologies. Conventional methods for brackish water desalination are limited by high-energy demands, especially in the low salinity range, prompting the exploration of electrochemical approaches like faradaic deionization. Sodium-manganese oxides, traditionally used in sodium-ion batteries, show promise as faradaic deionization electrode materials due to their abundance, low toxicity, and cost-effectiveness. However, capacity fading during cycling, often caused by structural changes, volume expansion, or chemical transformations, remains a critical challenge. This study investigates the impact of morphology and crystal structure on the electrochemical performance of commercial and synthesized sodium-manganese oxides for faradaic deionization applications. Structural and electrochemical characterization in three-electrode cells with low-concentration electrolytes provided insights into the charge storage mechanisms. Rocking-chair full flow cell experiments demonstrated that the mixed-phase sodium-manganese oxide exhibited superior desalination performance, achieving a high salt removal capacity of 54.5 mg g^{-1} and a mean value in the salt removal rate of $1.49 \text{ mg g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. Notably, mixed-phase sodium-manganese oxide maintained 98% capacity retention over 870 cycles, one of the longest reported cycling experiments in this field, effectively mitigating the Jahn-Teller effect. These findings highlight the crucial role of sodium-manganese oxide structure and morphology in electrochemical performance, positioning mixed-phase sodium-manganese oxide as a strong candidate for sustainable water treatment technologies.

context, desalination emerges as a critical player, offering hope to regions struggling with water scarcity. According to the analysis performed by Jones, there are almost 8000 brackish (BW) and river water desalination plants worldwide, accounting for 21% and 8% of global desalination capacity, respectively.^[3] In these cases, reverse osmosis (RO) and electrodialysis (ED) are the predominant technologies, which, while effective, fall short in terms of energy efficiency and cost-effectiveness, with energy requirements ranging from $0.5\text{--}0.6 \text{ kWh m}^{-3}$ for the BWRO to $0.4\text{--}0.9 \text{ kWh m}^{-3}$ for ED when reducing concentrations from 5 g L^{-1} to below 0.5 g L^{-1} .^[2,4-7] This challenge has led to research into electrochemical methods, holding the promise of high efficiency, especially in low concentrations.^[8] Against this backdrop, the rise of electrochemical ion separation processes presents an alternative desalination technology with several attractive features.^[9,10] These include environmental friendliness (electrons serve as the sole driving force rather than pressure or temperature gradients), high-energy efficiency, chemical-free operation (no additional chemicals are required), flexibility, easy scalability, potential for energy recovery, and cost-effectiveness.^[11,12] In contrast to conventional thermal and membrane processes that previously held prominence, these electrochemical methods place a primary emphasis on energy

1. Introduction

Water scarcity, a pressing global concern affecting up to 32.5% of the world's population, is exacerbated by the twin challenges of climate change and population growth.^[1,2] The quest for an ample supply of drinkable water intensifies as traditional sources become increasingly unreliable, with the number of large cities facing water scarcity under at least one scenario projected to increase to 55.5% by 2050.^[1] In this

efficiency, emerging as a promising avenue in the quest for sustainable water solutions, especially to desalinate low salinity water sources ($\approx 1\text{--}5 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ total dissolved solids).^[13-15]

Capacitive deionization (CDI) has emerged as a promising, environmental-benign alternative in the pursuit of efficient and cost-effective desalination.^[2,14,16-18] Its ion removal mechanism is based on the formation of an electric double-layer (EDL), distinguishing itself from conventional methods primarily focused on water extraction.^[8,19-21] The traditional CDI, known for its energy efficiency, utilizes porous carbon-based electrodes with high specific surface areas in a two-step process: electroadsorption and ion release by introducing the electrostatic force with a low direct electrical potential ($< 1.5 \text{ V}$).^[14,16,17] However, the dependence on specific surface area poses challenges, limiting salt removal efficiency and leading to issues such as moderate salt removal capacity (generally between 5 and 20

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mg_{NaCl} per gram of electrode).^[5] In response to these limitations, the exploration of battery-type electrode materials has gained momentum, leading to the process of faradaic deionization (FDI). In FDI, ions are removed through redox or intercalation mechanisms, offering superior selectivity, higher ion capture capacities, and improved charge efficiency.^[22,23] The first proof of concept of the “battery desalination” was published by Pasta et al. using a drop-casted sodium manganese oxide (NMO) carbon cloth electrode and a silver nanorod. Following that work, Lee et al.^[24] utilized tunnel-structured NMO in a hybrid capacitive deionization (HCDI) cell. In that study, NMO was employed alongside activated carbon (AC) and an anion-exchange membrane (AEM), achieving a salt adsorption capacity of 31 mg g⁻¹, which was regarded as the highest reported value at that time.^[25] However, while the majority of HCDI-related studies have focused on materials capable of removing Na⁺ ions, the use of carbon-based materials as Cl⁻-removing electrodes has hindered the broader application of HCDI. Different strategies have been explored to expand the salt removal capacity, for instance, replacing carbon electrodes with anion-selective electrodes such as silver, bismuth oxides, layered double hydroxides (LDHs), and polymer compounds.^[26,27] Another approach to address this limitation was investigated by Smith and Dmello^[28] who designed a novel symmetric faradaic desalination system, which eliminates the need for Cl⁻-removing electrodes, later termed rocking-chair deionization (RCDI). In their design, Na⁺ cations are chemically intercalated into the negative electrode and simultaneously deintercalated from the positive electrode, while Cl⁻ anions are driven through the anion-exchange membrane into the positive chamber. This mechanism allows for the continuous generation of concentrated and dilute streams at the negative and positive electrodes, respectively.^[17] However, the practical application of these faradaic electrode materials presents several demerits, especially the large volume changes and structural degradation of battery-type materials during continuous desalination operation, leading to lower stability and reversibility as compared to carbon electrodes.^[14]

Since the development of FDI systems, sodium–manganese oxides (with molecular form Na_xMnO₂) have garnered attention for their remarkable combination of high energy density, low toxicity, cost-effectiveness, and abundant raw materials.^[5,29] These oxides exhibit significant potential for storing Na⁺ in aqueous sodium-ion batteries and capacitor systems, making them an appealing choice for integration into the FDI system. NMO exists in several crystallographic forms with Mn in multiple valence states.^[29,30] These compounds generally possess an open crystal structure suitable for large ion insertion and extraction without distinct volume expansion. These materials generally show tunnel structures for 0 < x ≤ 0.44, a mixed tunnel and layered structures for 0.44 < x ≤ 0.66, and a fully layered structure for 0.66 < x ≤ 1.^[29] As previously mentioned, studies developed by Li's group at Nankai University explored the desalination performance of various crystallographic forms of NMO, primarily focusing on tunnel (T-NMO) and layered structures (O-NMO and P-NMO, where Na⁺ intercalate at octahedral and prismatic sites, respectively).^[29] This work, although highlighting the impact of different crystal structures on the desalination performance, only evaluated the FDI systems for a limited time (30 cycles, just 30 h), reaching desalination capacities below 50 mg g⁻¹ when using 50 mM NaCl solutions. Subsequent studies from the same group introduced the concept of a mixed-phase material (0.71Na_{0.55}Mn₂O₄@0.29Na_{0.7}MnO₂), which demonstrated a synergistic effect, reaching a high desalination capacity of 65 mg g⁻¹ and remarkable cyclability, with 95% capacity retention after 50 cycles.^[31]

Following the phase integration idea suggested by previous work, this paper delves into the study and application of three different types of NMOs as faradaic electrode materials for FDI, aiming to exploit their unique structural features and electrochemical properties: 1) commercial Na_{0.7}MnO_{2+δ}, when x falls within the range of 0.66 < x ≤ 1, Na_xMnO₂ materials adopt a layered structure, primarily classified into P2-type and O3-type. Previous reports indicate that the P2 phase offers higher capacity and faster ion transfer, making it particularly advantageous;^[32] 2) commercial Na_{0.44}MnO₂, this material is particularly attractive because of its adequate crystal structure, forming suitable large-size tunnels for sodium incorporation. This structural feature enables a high theoretical capacity of 121 mAh g⁻¹;^[33,34] and 3) a synthesized mix-phased composite (denoted as mp-NMO), which combines two different crystal phases, is designed to address the main drawback of NMO materials, the rapid structural degradation resulting in capacity loss.^[35]

By examining the impact of the morphology and crystal structures on the electrochemical performance of these materials, this study aims to contribute to the advancement of sustainable water treatment technologies, offering insights that could enhance emerging desalination processes such as FDI. Electrochemical analysis revealed that the mp-NMO material, with higher capacitive contributions, demonstrated superior stability at low salt concentrations, underscoring its potential for brackish water desalination applications. In full-flow deionization cell tests, the new material not only showed the highest salt removal capacity values in the first cycles, but also maintained SRC values around 54 mg g⁻¹ over 600 cycles. Additionally, cycling experiments and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis showed that this mixed-phase NMO effectively mitigates the Jahn-Teller effect, which typically causes Mn²⁺ dissolution and capacity fading in sodium manganese oxides. The process rate remained stable, indicating consistent cycle duration and maintained kinetics throughout the experiments. Thereby, these results show how crystal structure and morphology can enhance the electrochemical behavior for FDI and evidence the promising performance of mp-NMO for efficient sodium ion intercalation.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Morphology and Structure

X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were initially examined for commercial NMO samples (Na_{0.44}MnO₂ and Na_{0.7}MnO_{2+δ}). The refined XRD pattern of commercial Na_{0.44}MnO₂ (Figure S1a, Supporting Information) was consistent with the P6mm space group (JCPDS No. 27-0750).^[35] Notably, the XRD pattern displayed the presence of the (001) peak at low angles, indicating orientationally stacked MnO₂ nanosheets in the birnessite phase with interlayered ions.^[29,36] The crystal structure of this commercial Na_{0.44}MnO₂ comprises MnO₅ square pyramids and MnO₆ octahedra, forming two distinct tunnel structures—one larger with an S-shape and the other smaller pentagon-type. S-shaped tunnels, which serve as fast ion diffusion pathways, are ideal for large Na⁺ ions.^[35] Additionally, Mn⁴⁺ ions occupy MnO₆ octahedral sites, with half of the Mn³⁺ ions residing in MnO₅ square pyramids and the other half in MnO₆ octahedra, contributing also to the fast diffusion of Na⁺ ions.^[35]

The diffraction peaks of the sample of Na_{0.7}MnO_{2+δ} (Figure S1b, Supporting Information) can be indexed to a P2-type layered structure, with a hexagonal Na_{0.7}MnO_{2+δ} phase (JCPDF: 27-0751), showing the

diffraction peaks located at 15.8° , 36.0° , 39.7° , 49.0° , and 64.8° assigned to crystallographic planes (002), (100), (102), (104), and (110), respectively.^[32,37,38] For $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+\delta}$, the structure involves the distribution of $[\text{Mn}^{3+}\text{O}_6]^{3-}$ and $[\text{Mn}^{4+}\text{O}_6]^{2-}$ structures within transition metal-oxide layers. While a fully stoichiometric NaMnO_2 structure is anticipated under normal conditions, the presence of Na vacancies results in the formation of the Na-deficient $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+\delta}$ structure, with one vacancy occurring in every six MnO_6 octahedra.^[39]

The XRD analysis of the NMO prepared with the new synthesis procedure, defined as mp-NMO, was performed in two steps (Figure 1, P1 and P2), first after the initial calcination at 450°C (Figure 1a) and then after the second calcination at 900°C (Figure 1e).

In the first calcination, $\text{Na}_2\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_7$ material was found as the primary material, known by its triclinic structure, which has a mixed valence state of manganese (Mn^{4+} and Mn^{3+}) that could enhance redox activity.^[40] Using the L_{23} ratio approach from M. Varela et al.^[41] to calculate the manganese oxidation state, the results obtained from the ARM200cF scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) at 200 kV indicate that the observed structure aligns with Mn^{4+} (Figure S2a, Supporting Information). This is consistent with the $\text{Na}_2\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_7$ phase, particularly in elongated nanoparticle morphologies. This oxide material is based on parallel layers of $[\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_7]^{2-}$ built up with edge-sharing MnO_6 octahedra,^[23] leaving one out of seven Mn vacancies in the transition metal layer, oxygen displays a distorted P3-type stack, and Na^+ occupies both a distorted prism and octahedral sites.^[40,42] Another interesting fact about this material is that, contrary to the reported studies on layered Na_xMnO_2 , no amorphization and/or increase of disordered and stacking faults is observed, which is due to the fact that the insertion process is occurring through only one biphasic process, suggesting a topotactic structural transformation.^[23]

After the second calcination, a mixture of phases was observed (Figure 1e), including the previously identified structure and the β - NaMnO_2 phase (Figure S2b, Supporting Information). β - NaMnO_2 adopts an orthorhombic structure (Pmmn) known for its ability to

undergo redox reactions involving Mn^{4+} and Mn^{3+} states, accompanied by the intercalation and deintercalation of Na^+ ions.^[43] The presence of the (001) peak at low angles in the XRD patterns means that MnO_2 nanosheets are stacked orientationally in the birnessite phase (JCPDS No. 43-1456) with interlayered Na^+ ions.^[36] This material shows one of the highest theoretical capacities among sodium manganites, approaching 234.8mAh g^{-1} ,^[43] which could be quite interesting for Na^+ capture. In this structure, the MnO_6 sheets buckle, forming a peculiar, packed layered structure where sodium ions are hexacoordinated in the zigzag interlayers. However, the main disadvantage of this material is its oxidation state (Mn^{3+}) which could suffer the Jahn-Teller distortion. Our hypothesis here is that the combination of both phases ($\text{Na}_2\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_7$ and β - NaMnO_2) mitigates structural degradation during cycling, with $\text{Na}_2\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_7$ providing stability through reversible phase transformations and β - NaMnO_2 contributing robustness via its layered configuration. According to the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) method, the surface area of this novel material is $3\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$, which is lower than the other two materials ($4\text{--}5$ and $5\text{--}6\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$ for $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$ and $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+\delta}$, respectively, Figure S3, Supporting Information) due to a higher particle size and more homogeneous particle distribution as per obtained through SEM imaging. The density functional theory (DFT) model for pore size distribution curve reveals that the average pore size of the material is about 5.6 nm, indicating the existence of mesopores and macropores (Figure S4, Supporting Information).

SEM and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) analysis of the samples before (Figure 1b–d) and after (Figure 1f–h) the thermal calcination at 900°C for 15 h was also conducted. The elemental mapping of both samples illustrates the homogeneous distribution of the elements in the composite. Figures 1f,g display that the material after calcination showed anisotropic prismatic crystallites elongated in rod shapes, corresponding to the orthorhombic β - NaMnO_2 , proving therefore a partial reduction of Mn(IV) to Mn(III), which aligns well with the XRD spectra. Further analysis using the JEOL JEM-2100

Figure 1. Structural analysis of the mp-NMO material before (P1) and after (P2) the calcination at 900°C for 15 h. Results of a, e) the XRD spectra, b, f) SEM at $\times 1000$, c, g) at $\times 10\,000$, d, h) and EDS analysis.

Figure 2. Crystal structure (reproduced with VESTA software) of β - NaMnO_2 and $\text{Na}_2\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_7$.

transmission electron microscope (TEM) revealed that the interplanar spacing of 6.34 Å corresponds to the b-axis parameter of the orthorhombic phase of NaMnO_2 (Figure S2b, Supporting Information). The mean values of the dimensions of these rods were $3.69 \pm 1.21 \mu\text{m}$ in length and $0.98 \pm 0.40 \mu\text{m}$ in lateral size (Figure S5, Supporting Information), showing therefore an aggregation of the previous particles and a shape transformation, leading to bigger dimensions in comparison with the commercial materials (~ 1.1 and $\sim 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ for $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$ and $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+\delta}$, respectively). Additionally, the ICP-OES (Table S1, Supporting Information) results indicate that the atomic ratio Na:Mn is approaching 1:1, suggesting the synthesis of β - NaMnO_2 , which agrees with both the XRD and EDS. Therefore, the mp-NMO was based on a combination of β - NaMnO_2 (ICSD 16271) and $\text{Na}_2\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_7$ (ICSD 01-078-0193) (Figure 2).

2.2. Electrochemical Performance in a Three-Electrode Cell

The electrochemical characterization of the NMO electrodes was performed using two electrolyte concentrations, 0.5 and 0.05 M NaCl (Figure 3). The 0.5 M concentration was chosen to ensure a high ion availability, minimizing resistivity issues and facilitating a detailed investigation of the electrochemical behavior of the materials under study. In contrast, the 0.05 M concentration was selected to simulate natural water conditions, as it corresponds to approximately 3 g L^{-1} NaCl, representative of medium to low salinity levels typically found in brackish waters. This procedure to evaluate deionization materials was also suggested elsewhere.^[44]

As shown in Figure 3a,b, the tunnel structure of commercial $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$ offers the highest capacity among all the electrodes tested at high electrolyte concentrations. However, when the electrolyte concentration was decreased, a significant reduction in capacity from 43 to 25 mAh g^{-1} was observed (Figure 3b,d) due to the increased resistance component associated with the electrolyte and the lower Na^+ availability. Notably, the commercial $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+\delta}$ electrode demonstrated the highest specific capacity (33 mAh g^{-1}) under these conditions (Figure 3d). For the commercial $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$, another important

difference was observed in the number of reversible peaks (as represented in Equation 1) decreasing from three at 0.5 M to two at 0.05 M (Figure 3a,c):

A similar behavior was observed in commercial $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+\delta}$, where at high concentrations, a pair of smooth redox peaks at approximately 0.2/0.5 V were visible (Figure S6, Supporting Information), attributed to the $\text{Mn}^{4+}/\text{Mn}^{3+}$ valence variation.^[38] However, at low concentrations, these peaks almost disappear as the reduced availability of Na^+ ions diminishes the driving force for ion transport and increases resistance, leading to slower reaction kinetics. This does not imply incomplete reactions but indicates a shift in the mechanism.

At lower ionic concentrations, the contribution of surface-controlled processes becomes more pronounced relative to bulk-controlled processes. Consequently, the charge and discharge profiles lack well-defined plateaus, reflecting the predominance of capacitive-like behavior under these conditions.

On the other hand, the combination of β - NaMnO_2 and $\text{Na}_2\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_7$, resulting in the mp-NMO material produces a CV curve with less defined redox peaks compared to the previous materials. Although the $\text{Mn}^{4+}/\text{Mn}^{3+}$ redox couple of β - NaMnO_2 typically provides clear peaks in the CV, they become significantly broadened, especially at low NaCl concentrations. These changes are primarily influenced by variations in the ionic environment, ion transport dynamics, and the electrode's interaction with the electrolyte. As mentioned above, at lower NaCl concentrations (0.05 M), the reduced availability of Na^+ ions for intercalation can lead to diminished redox activity at the electrode.^[36] This reduction in Na^+ ions results in the disappearance of peaks associated with specific $\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{4+}$ redox transitions.^[35,45]

To further understand the electrochemical behavior of these materials at low NaCl concentrations, the changes induced by the scan rate in the CVs were also analyzed using Dunn and Lindstrom methods to evaluate the capacitive and faradaic contributions (Figure 4).^[46,47] The analysis of the $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+\delta}$ electrodes (Figure 4a,b) showed how the two visible anodic peaks are covered by a capacitive contribution, which becomes dominant as the rate is increased (Figure 4c). Reversely, for the $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$, which is the material with the smallest particle size, the behavior is mainly faradaic at low scan rates (53%) with very well-defined peaks even at high scan rates (Figure 4d,e). Despite the disappearance of the lower voltage peaks observed as the NaCl concentration was reduced (Figure 3), it is still possible to identify them through the deconvolution of the Faradaic contribution, Figure 4e, although slightly shifted to the voltage window edge and mostly hidden due to the capacitive currents.

Interestingly, the behavior of the mp-NMO sits in between the other two materials. It exhibits pronounced peaks, particularly the anodic ones, with a b-value around 0.5 indicating a diffusion-limited process. This is consistent with the deconvolution of the faradaic and capacitive currents obtained by Dunn's method (Figure 4g,h).^[47] The redox reaction is so favorable that it inhibits any capacitive contribution around

Figure 3. CV and GCD cycles of the different samples performed at a, b) 0.5 M and c, d) 0.05 M.

the peak voltage, implying that the ion selectivity at these voltages is substantially higher than in either of the other two materials. Nevertheless, at low NaCl concentrations and across the entire voltage range, the majority of the charge still comes from the double layer capacitance (DLC) (Figure 4i).

It is also important to mention that the total charge accumulated in a capacitive way is always constant for an electrode over different scan rates (Figure 4c,f,i). To understand the nature of this capacitance, equivalent NMO-free electrodes only composed of the conductive additive (Ketjen), binder (PVDF), and current collector (avCarb P75T-40) were prepared and analyzed under the same conditions (Figure S7, Supporting Information). The capacitance of this material is purely DLC, a feature common in carbon-based electrodes, which is further confirmed by the rectangular shape of the voltammograms.^[48] This electrode has a surface area substantially higher than that of the NMO-based electrodes: $103 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ compared to the $40 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ of the $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+\delta}$, $30 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ of the $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$, and $21 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ of the mp-NMO. Still, its capacitance is significantly lower than in the case of the NMO electrodes, as shown in Figure 4c,f,i, where the red dashed line indicates the capacitance of the equivalent NMO-free DLC electrode. The comparison between the NMO-free electrode and the different NMO electrodes is further expanded in Figure S8, Supporting Information. The findings indicate that only a fraction of the capacitance observed in the NMO electrodes comes from DLC, and the vast majority of the charge accumulation stems from pseudocapacitive processes. This is significant because it suggests that, beyond the selective charge accumulation observed in purely faradaic, battery-type peaks, a large part of the overall capacitance may also exhibit selectivity. While pseudocapacitance typically allows for the accommodation of various cations within a material's structure—as observed in materials like MXenes and MnO_2 ^[49,50]—the unique structural and compositional

characteristics of sodium manganese oxides (NMOs) promote a selective affinity for Na^+ ions.^[51] While pseudocapacitance itself is not inherently selective, since it can accommodate various cations in the structure (as seen with MXenes and MnO_2 ^[49,50]), the specific structure and composition of NMOs favor Na^+ selectivity.^[51] This inherent selectivity renders NMOs particularly suitable for desalination applications.^[52,53]

Once the redox mechanisms were analyzed, the stability of the electrodes, which is a paramount metric to determine the capacity fading, especially at low concentrations, was evaluated. The results of the galvanostatic cycling over 100 cycles of the different NMO electrodes compared at high and low concentrations are shown in Figure 5a,b, respectively.

Consistent with previous results shown in Figure 3, reducing the electrolyte concentration led to a decrease in specific capacity across all materials. However, the extent of this reduction was not equal for all the materials. For $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$, the capacity dropped by 50% (from 53.8 to 26.8 mAh g^{-1}), whereas for the layered materials, the reduction was significantly lower, only 16% for mp-NMO (from 27.4 to

20.3 mAh g^{-1}) and negligible for $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+\delta}$.

Examining the evolution of specific capacity during cycling, $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$ electrodes exhibited capacity fading in both high and low concentrated electrolytes. After 100 cycles, a 20% decrease was observed at 0.5 M (43.3 mAh g^{-1}) while a 33% reduction occurred at 0.05 M (18.0 mAh g^{-1}). In contrast, the layered materials displayed a more stable performance in which, even though a small decay was observed, the capacity reduction was far less pronounced. Notably, $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_2$ maintained over 100% capacity retention in high-concentration electrolytes, revealing an expansion of the electrochemical performance (capacity of 39.8 mAh g^{-1} after 100 cycles). This behavior is likely linked to lattice changes in the crystal structure, leading to multiphase transitions during cycling.^[54] In 0.05 M NaCl, $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_2$ retained 92% of its capacity after 100 cycles, although it exhibited lower coulombic efficiency than $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$, likely due to higher internal resistance.

Meanwhile, the mp-NMO initially exhibited a capacity increase in the first few cycles, likely due to an electrochemical activation process that enhanced sodium storage with repeated cycling.^[38,55] After 100 cycles, mp-NMO retained a discharge capacity of 27.0 and 19.9 mAh g^{-1} , showing excellent capacity retention not only at high electrolyte concentrations (99%) but also at low ones (98%). Its outstanding stability can be attributed to the presence of $\text{Na}_2\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_7$, which acts as a structural stabilizer, mitigating phase transitions and volume changes typically affecting $\beta\text{-NaMnO}_2$ during cycling. This stabilization helps preserve the integrity of the electrode material, ensuring superior long-term performance. The high capacity retention suggests a reduction of the Jahn-Teller effect, which is commonly associated with Mn^{2+} dissolution and capacity fading in sodium manganese oxides.^[31,35,40] The mitigation mechanism will be further explored in the following sections, which focus on investigating salt removal performance.

Figure 4. CVs performed at different scan rates using low concentration electrolyte 50 mM NaCl and contributions analysis for a–c) $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+\delta}$, d–f) $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$, and g–i) mp-NMO. Corresponding capacitive and faradaic contributions deconvoluted by Dunn’s method as well as the b -value for each of the observable peak obtained by Lindstrom method (b, e, h).^[46,47] Capacity and capacitance values normalized by the electrode mass for each scan rate and materials c, f, i).

2.3. Desalination Performance: Studies in Full Cell

2.3.1. Effect of the Crystal Structure of the NMOs

To study the effect of the crystal structure of the different NMOs on the desalination performance, cycling stability experiments were conducted in the full symmetric cell under constant current mode (0.05 A g^{-1} , which corresponds to a scan rate of around 0.4 mV s^{-1}). The tests were performed using a 0.05 M NaCl electrolyte concentration, equivalent to a $\approx 3 \text{ g L}^{-1}$.

The results displayed in **Figure 6a** show that $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$ shows the highest specific discharge capacity in the first cycles (51.5 mAh g^{-1} for the first cycle, **Figure 6a**) while $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+\delta}$ and mp-NMO amounted to 38.0 and 41.5 mAh g^{-1} , respectively. However, after 100 cycles, the mp-NMO was the one displaying the highest capacity (31.7 mAh g^{-1}) reaching also an impressive capacity retention of 96% (**Figure 6a**). This result contrasts with the capacity retention values obtained for layered-type NMO ($\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+\delta}$) and tunnel-type ($\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$), achieving only 69% and 61%, respectively, along with significantly lower discharge capacities (24.5 and 22.8 mAh g^{-1} , respectively).

Figure 5. Stability galvanostatic plots performed at 0.1 A g^{-1} , equivalent to 0.7 mV s^{-1} , using a voltage window between 0 and 1 V in a) 0.5 M NaCl and b) 0.05 M NaCl .

Figure 6. Electrochemical studies of the full flow cell in 0.05 M NaCl solution applying 0.05 A g^{-1} (approximately 0.4 mV s^{-1}) in the $\pm 0.8 \text{ V}$ range: a) cycling stability test over 100 cycles; b) salt removal capacity response of the different NMO materials.

To further investigate these trends, differential capacity (dQ/dV) plots, a technique commonly used in battery research to identify degradation mechanisms such as material loss, dendrite formation, electrolyte degradation, or phase change, were analyzed (Figure S10, Supporting Information).^[56] Notably, this study represents the first application of dQ/dV analysis to evaluate degradation in an electrochemical deionization system. The evolution of these graphs indicates that both layered and tunnel NMOs experienced substantial active material loss and worsening kinetics, as evidenced by the reduced peak intensity and broader peaks.^[56] In contrast, the mp-NMO primarily exhibited peak shifts, suggesting minor active material loss or compositional changes, which did not significantly impact capacity retention. These observations align with the capacity evolution trends shown in Figure 6.

Finally, the cycling stability experiments conducted in the flow cell at 0.05 A g^{-1} (Figure 6b) revealed notable differences compared to those performed at 0.1 A g^{-1} in the three-electrode cell (Figure 5b). This variation can be primarily attributed to the reduction in current density, as lower current densities often result in higher initial capacity values. However, this enhancement occurs under more demanding electrochemical conditions, leading to a faster decline in capacity retention. Notably, the flow cell experiments underscored the significant robustness of the mixed-phase sodium manganese oxide (mp-NMO)

material, which exhibited stable performance with excellent cycling stability, irrespective of the applied current densities and cell configurations.

The analysis of the conductivity and its conversion to salt concentration difference demonstrated a critical impact of the NMO crystal structure on the deionization capacity. The tunnel-type ($\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$) electrode exhibited the highest SRC values in the initial cycles, reaching $60\text{--}70 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$ within the first 10 cycles. This result is supported by GCD plots (Figure 6a and Figure S9a, Supporting Information) and aligns with the literature.^[8] Additionally, the SRC values obtained in the initial cycles are quite competitive compared to previous studies on $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$, which achieved SRC values of 50 mg g^{-1} in 50 mM NaCl .^[29] However, for long-term cycling stability (Figure 5b), layered-type materials with a higher capacitive contribution (Figure 4c,i) at that charging rate showed better stability. Specifically, $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+8}$ retained 67% of its capacity after 80 cycles starting with a SRC value of 37 mg g^{-1} (Figure 5c). This improved stability is likely attributed to a lattice distortion of the MnO_6 octahedra slices facilitating the Na^+ insertion/extraction.^[57] Finally, the mp-NMO electrode exhibited the highest capacity retention (over 100%), with a SRC value of 54 mg g^{-1} after 80 cycles (Figure 6b), surpassing the individual NMOs that form the mixed phase, which range from 28 to 40 mg g^{-1} for $\text{NaMnO}_2//\text{AC}$ in $\approx 10 \text{ mM}$.^[36] This achievement could be attributed to the synergistic effect

of the open porous structure of NaMnO_2 and the lamellar structure of Na_2MnO_7 , which provides a high interfacial area for Na^+ ion intercalation.^[29,40] Additionally, from the kinetics perspective, SRR values were quite similar for all the NMOs (Figure S9b, Supporting Information), ranging from 1.2 to $1.8 \text{ mg g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$, reaching comparable SRR values of $1.8\text{--}2.5 \text{ mg g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ reported in literature with carbon-based materials.^[14,58–60]

2.3.2. Mechanism Analysis

During FDI operation, commonly, two redox processes occur in $\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{4+}$ -based NMO samples. The primary redox couple involves the highly reversible intercalation/deintercalation of Na^+ ions within the NMO host lattice (Equation 1). Concurrently, a side reaction occurs, wherein Mn^{3+} undergoes disproportionation into Mn^{4+} and Mn^{2+} , the latter of which dissolves into the electrolyte, leading to mass loss and capacity fading over prolonged operation.^[31,35,40] That process is commonly referred to as Jahn-Teller effect. As in the case of battery performance, it is assumed that this core mechanism governs the differences in desalination capacity and electrochemical performance among NMO samples. To further delve into the degradation source of the studied NMO materials, XPS analysis (Figure 7) was performed to study the

Figure 7. XPS Mn 2p spectra of a) $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$, b) $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+\delta}$, and c) mp-NMO.

evolution of the Mn^{3+} and Mn^{4+} species before and after the 100 cycles stability test in the flow cell.

XPS analysis revealed that the proportion of Mn^{3+} species decreased by 8.9% in $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$ and 3% in $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+\delta}$, after the cycling experiments, indicating a partial reduction of Mn^{4+} to Mn^{3+} (Table S2, Supporting Information).^[29,36] This trend correlates with the observed decline in desalination capacity among the different crystallographic NMO materials. The varying degrees of $\text{Mn}^{4+}/\text{Mn}^{3+}$ redox activity suggest that each phase exhibits a distinct Na^+ intercalation/deintercalation capability, directly influencing desalination performance. Consequently, the progressive oxidation of Mn and partial disproportionation, with the associated structural modifications, contribute to the performance degradation observed upon cycling.

On the other hand, XPS analysis of mp-NMO reveals that the $\text{Mn}^{4+}/\text{Mn}^{3+}$ ratio remains unchanged after cycling, indicating a stable Mn oxidation state with minimal redox fluctuation. This suggests a robust Mn oxidation environment, contributing to the material's structural resilience during charge–discharge cycles. However, the Mn:Na ratio shifts significantly from 1:4 in the fresh electrode to 3:1 after cycling, confirming extensive Na deintercalation (Table S2, Supporting Information). Concurrently, XPS O 1s spectra show a reduction in Mn–O bonding, indicative of structural rearrangements or oxygen loss, which may contribute to minor degradation. Post-cycling, the Na 1s peak shifts slightly to 1071.6 eV, exhibiting two closely spaced contributions, suggesting a redistribution of sodium species or the formation of distinct Na bonding environments (Figure S11, Supporting Information). These variations can be attributed to structural changes or rearrangements occurring during the first cycles, after which the material stabilizes, as confirmed by electrochemical cycling stability tests. This behavior highlights mp-NMO's initial adjustments to electrochemical stress, followed by sustained stability in Mn oxidation states, despite sodium loss and minor oxygen depletion. Such characteristics contribute to its relatively stable long-term electrochemical performance compared to the other two NMO systems (Figure 6).

2.3.3. Operational Outputs of the Different NMOs

Considering the desalination experiments performed in the flow cell, operational outputs such as E_M and P were calculated and compared for the different NMO electrodes. As shown in Figure 8, the mp-NMO electrode demonstrated the lowest energy consumption, showing a

decreasing trend in the E_M values while maintaining stable production performance at approximately $80 \text{ L h}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$, which is consistent with the SRC results. These values are comparable to other symmetric cells, although showing very low E_V (below 0.01 kWh m^{-3}).^[58] Both $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$ and $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+\delta}$ displayed an increasing trend in E_M and P values, primarily driven by the decrease in SRC and the reduction in discharging time, respectively, which were attributed to the electrode degradation over cycling. From the technology scaling-up point of view, P is expected to have a strong impact on capital costs, while E_M will influence operating costs. This implies that P and E_M could serve as approximate surrogates for capital and operational costs, respectively.^[44]

Given its high stability in terms of galvanostatic performance and salt removal capacity, the mixed-phase NMO material was selected for further study.

2.3.4. Stability Tests of mp-NMO

A long-term test was conducted over 870 cycles using the FDI cell equipped with mp-NMO and the same experimental conditions (0.05 M NaCl solution applying 0.05 A g^{-1} in the $\pm 0.8 \text{ V}$ range). The experiment demonstrates the outstanding performance of the mp-NMO electrodes, achieving a specific discharge capacity of 30 mAh g^{-1} , maintaining a nearly stable performance throughout more than 40 days of operation, showing a capacity retention of 98% (Figure S12, Supporting Information).

The SRC values obtained from the conductivity (only recorded for 600 cycles, Figure 9a) follow a consistent trend with an average value of 55 mg g^{-1} , reaching maximum values of $\sim 65 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$ during the operation. These results are higher than other FDI systems based on NMOs reported in the literature, such as the $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_2$ ones employed by Zhao et al. that achieved 50 mg g^{-1} applying 1 V or the $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$ used by Lee et al. that reached an SRC of 30 mg g^{-1} under the same electrolyte conditions. Additionally, the work of Wang et al., in which both NaMnO_2 and CNT/NaMnO_2 were used, reported 40 and 43 mg g^{-1} , respectively, when using an electrolyte with a substantially higher concentration (0.34 M NaCl).^[24,29,36] Furthermore, Liu et al.^[5] achieved 45 mg g^{-1} when testing an HC DI system $\text{Na}_{0.55}\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O/PPBC-3 HC}$ in a 20 mm NaCl electrolyte solution. Regarding efficiency, the high correlation between the theoretical salt removal capacity values calculated from the galvanostatic charge–

Figure 8. Performance of the full-cell using different active materials. Operational parameters such as a) E_M and b) P were analyzed over cycling experiments.

Figure 9. Long-term electrochemical performance of the mp-NMO full flow cell in 50 mM NaCl using 0.05 A g^{-1} in the $\pm 0.8 \text{ V}$ range: a) SRC values; b) SRR values; c) analysis of the operational outputs such as P and E_V . d) Kim-Yoon plot including the performance of the CDI and FDI systems observed in the literature along with the results obtained in this study.

discharge curves (Figure 9a red line) and the SRC data obtained from ionic conductivity measurements (Figure 9a orange line) is noteworthy (80%). This correlation highlights the relationship between the transferred electrical charge and the salt deficiency or excess in the effluent stream. It also demonstrates the effectiveness of the electron transfer mechanism associated with sodium intercalation.^[44] The data from the cycling experiments, as well as from the XPS post-mortem analysis, demonstrated that this mixed-phase NMO seems to effectively mitigate the primary issue associated with sodium manganese oxides: the Jahn-Teller effect.^[31,35,40] Additionally, the rate of the process remained constant (Figure 9b), indicating that the cycles were not shortened and the kinetics of the process were maintained.

To tentatively analyze the costs of the system and assess the practical viability of this new material in the long-term, a study of the operational variables E_V and P is described (Figure 9c). Regarding the capital cost, it was observed that P exhibited quite high values (between 60 and $80 \text{ L h}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$) even for a faradaic material. This can be attributed to the relatively fast process, thanks to its capacitive contribution. Moreover, E_V remained low and constant for this cell, yielding competitive results compared to other faradaic symmetric systems.^[7,61] Finally, the Kim-Yoon plot (Figure 9d) clearly shows the outstanding performance of the symmetric NMO's cells in comparison with reported CDI and FDI systems, reaching competitive high salt removal capacities and salt capture rates.^[62]

2.3.5. Brackish River Scenario

To evaluate the efficiency of the FDI circular cell equipped with mp-NMO electrodes under more realistic conditions, an electrolyte solution was prepared mimicking the composition of a brackish river wall located in the southeast of Spain, which was characterized by a molar ratio of $\text{Na}^+:\text{K}^+:\text{Ca}^{2+}$ of 40:1:4, among others. Initially, the material's stability was assessed through cyclic voltammetry experiments by comparing its performance in NaCl electrolyte (Figure S13, Supporting Information). The presence of a distinct redox peak confirmed the material's stability in this complex ionic environment.

To further evaluate the potential of the mp-NMO electrodes, the FDI cell was tested by alternating between simulated brackish water and a 50 mM NaCl solution to compare the performance (Figure 10a). Assuming conductivity variations were primarily due to sodium chloride removal, the same calibration curve previously used was here employed. The results shown in Figure 10a revealed that, regardless of the water composition, both the specific capacity and the SRC remained stable with no observable degradation. The mean SRC value was 45 mg g^{-1} , and the retention of the capacity was 73% after 20 cycles (12 cycles with the mixture – 4 cycles with 50 mM NaCl, and another 4 cycles with the mixture). These values were corroborated by theoretical calculations based on the charge transferred during discharging, showing differences of less than 20% in most cases (Figure 9a). Additionally, ion chromatography (IC) measurements (Table S3, Supporting Information) conducted during cycling in the mixed cation solution revealed a molar removal ratio (ρ) of 40% for Na^+ over K^+ selectivity, indicating a preference for sodium ions. However, this selectivity decreased when comparing Na^+ to Ca^{2+} , yielding a value of 18%. This suggests that the mp-

Figure 10. Stability tests performed in the voltage range of ± 0.8 V at 0.04 A g^{-1} of the full cell mp-NMO in 25 mL of a solution composed by 0.05 M Na^+ , 0.001 M K^+ , 0.006 M Ca^{2+} , and 0.062 M Cl^- . a) Cycling stability plot with its corresponding theoretical and obtained SRC values per cycle working in the mixed solution (square dots) and the NaCl solution (circular dots). b) Long galvanostatic stability cycling in the mixed solution.

NMO layers exhibit limited selectivity for divalent cations, likely due to the stronger electrostatic interactions between Ca^{2+} and its hydration shell, which reduce its effective ionic radius.

To assess the robustness of the mp-NMO electrodes, the FDI cell was subjected to 80 cycles using simulated brackish water (Figure 10b). The system exhibited an initial specific capacity of 39 $mAh\ g^{-1}$ and a SRC of 45.6 $mg\ g^{-1}$ (average values of cycles 5–10), consistent with the values obtained in the NaCl solution (Figure 6c). After 80 cycles, the specific capacitance was reduced to just 28 $mAh\ g^{-1}$, accounting for a capacity retention of 72%. Additionally, energy consumption values remained around 0.013 $kWh\ m^{-3}$, similar to results obtained with NaCl solution. These metrics confirm the stability of mp-NMO electrodes in complex electrolytes containing both mono- and divalent cations.

3. Conclusion

A mixed-phase sodium manganese oxide (mp-NMO), composed of β - $NaMnO_2$ and $Na_2Mn_3O_7$ phases, was successfully synthesized. Its performance was evaluated alongside two commercial NMOs with distinct crystalline structures, $Na_{0.44}MnO_2$ and $Na_{0.7}MnO_{2+\delta}$, as electrode materials for brackish water desalination in a rocking chair FDI system. The electrochemical analysis of the mixed-phase NMO revealed a predominant capacitive contribution, demonstrating superior stability at low salt concentrations and highlighting its potential for desalination applications. In full-flow deionization cell tests, the new material maintained SRC values around 54.5 $mg\ g^{-1}$ over 870 cycles. Cycling experiments further confirmed that this mixed-phase NMO effectively mitigates the Jahn-Teller effect, typically responsible for Mn^{2+} dissolution and capacity fading in sodium manganese oxides. These results were also supported by dQ/dV analysis (used for the first time in electrochemical deionization in this study) and XPS post-mortem analysis. Additionally, the process rate remained stable in both simple NaCl solutions and simulated brackish water conditions, maintaining consistent cycle duration and kinetics with moderate selectivity for monovalent cations. These findings illustrate how the crystal structure and morphology of NMOs can significantly enhance electrochemical performance for FDI, reinforcing the potential of mixed-phase NMO

for efficient sodium ion intercalation and sustainable desalination applications.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: Sodium nitrate ($NaNO_3$; >97%) was purchased from EssentQ[®], manganese (II) nitrate tetrahydrate ($Mn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$; >97%), monohydrated citric acid ($C_6H_8O_7 \cdot H_2O$; >97%), sodium manganese oxide ($Na_{0.44}MnO_2$ and $Na_{0.7}MnO_{2+\delta}$), 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP; $\geq 99\%$), and sodium chloride ($NaCl$; $\geq 99\%$) were all purchased from Sigma Aldrich. KetjenBlack EC-600JD (CBK), polyvinylidene fluoride HSV900 (PVDF), and carbon nanotube sheet (AvCarbon P75T) were purchased from Nanografi, MTI corporation, and Fuel Cell Storage, respectively; and all chemicals were used as received without further purification. mp-NMO was synthesized by a sol-gel method, mixing 2.45 g of $NaNO_3$ and 6.72 g of $Mn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ in a solution of 12 g of citric acid in 8 g of H_2O , followed by a heat pre-treatment at 450 °C for 6 h and then a calcination at 900 °C for 15 h, a variation previously described.^[63] As a result, the molar ratio of sodium to manganese ions in our study was maintained at 0.94:1.00. The synthesis of sodium manganese oxides requires precise control over precursor molar ratios and processing conditions to ensure reproducibility. Thus, it is important to highlight that the resulting NMO phases can vary significantly depending on the specific synthesis approach and conditions employed. For instance, Zhao et al.^[31] synthesized a phase-integrated sodium manganese oxide (mix of $Na_{0.7}MnO_2$ and $Na_{0.55}Mn_2O_4$) using a one-step high-temperature calcination method with a $Na_2CO_3:Mn_2O_3$ molar ratio of 2:1 at 750 – 850 °C. Their findings revealed a strong correlation between the calcination temperature and the phase composition, where the fraction of the $Na_{0.55}Mn_2O_4$ phase decreased as the calcination temperature increased.

Fabrication of the electrode: The electrode was prepared following the proportions described by Xu et al.^[63] It involved using 80% of the active material (NMO: commercial $Na_{0.44}MnO_2$, commercial $Na_{0.7}MnO_{2+\delta}$, and mp-NMO), 10% of a conductive additive (CBK), and 10% of a binder (PVDF), with NMP as the solvent. For the three-electrode cell experiments, the mixture was stirred until, obtaining an ink with sufficient fluidity for lamination. Subsequently, lamination was performed using the Doctor Blade technique. The ink was deposited onto a carbon nanotube sheet, placed on an automatic laminator (MSK-AFA-II, MTI Corporation), and a thickness of 45 μm was set. On the other hand, for full-cell electrodes, the mixture was stirred until a more diluted ink was obtained for drop casting the 9.62 cm^2 carbon nanotube current collectors. After lamination/drop casting, it was air-dried for 1 h. After that, the sheet was placed in the oven at 70 °C for proper drying for 12 h. Once the drying was completed, the laminate was perforated into the desired shape and size. For three-electrode cells, NMO 10 mm diameter electrodes were prepared with mass loadings of around 3 $mg\ cm^{-2}$, while for the symmetric full-cell experiments, the mass loadings were 25 – 30 $mg\ cm^{-2}$.

Materials characterizations: The phases, structures, and morphologies of the electrode materials were characterized by X-ray diffraction spectrometry (XRD, Empyrean PANalytical) using a $Cu\ K\alpha$ source within the 10 – 70 2θ angle range, field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, JEOL JSM-7900F Prime) at an acceleration voltage of 15 kV equipped with EDS. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) imaging was conducted using a JEOL JEM-2100 operating at an acceleration voltage of 200 kV. High-resolution scanning transmission electron microscopy (HR-STEM) was performed using a JEOL ARM200CF equipped with a probe spherical aberration corrector at 200 kV. The imaging and structural characterization were performed in both bright-field (BF) and high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) modes to capture fine structural details and compositional contrasts. The nitrogen adsorption–desorption isotherms were measured using Micromeritics ASAP 2020 at 77 K, and the specific surface area was calculated using both the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) method for analyzing micro-meso-macro porous materials. Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES, Perkin Elmer Optima 7300 DV) was employed to determine

the atomic weight of the materials by performing an acid digestion with aqua regia in a closed reactor at 100 °C for 12 h. Additionally, the pre- and post-intercalated NMO electrode samples taken out from a typical cycle of desalination test (100 cycles) were monitored by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, FlexPS-ARPES-E_SPECS) to illustrate the variation of composition and chemical and electronic states during the desalination process and examined by XRD to elucidate the structural change during the desalination process.

Electrochemical experiments: A standard flooded three-electrode electrochemical cell was assembled using NMO as the working electrode, platinum mesh as the counter electrode, and Ag/AgCl (3 M NaCl) as the reference electrode in 0.05 M NaCl-based aqueous electrolytes. The experiments were carried out on a Biologic VMP3 multichannel Potentiostat/Galvanostat (Biologic SP-150). For the cyclic voltammetry (CV), the different NMO materials were studied first with a scan rate of 0.5 mV s⁻¹ over a potential range from 0 to 1 V in 0.5 and 0.05 M NaCl. Then, to obtain the faradaic and capacitive contributions, CVs of the fresh electrodes were performed after IR correction at 0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 0.7, and 1 mV s⁻¹ from 0 to 0.9 V. The Lindstrom and Dunn method was applied through a custom-made python script.^[46,47] For the long-term cycling stability test, galvanostatic charge and discharge (GCD) cycles were performed at 0.1 A g⁻¹ within the potential window between 0 and 1 V in 0.5 and 0.05 M NaCl.

Desalination test: After studying the three different intercalation materials in a three-electrode configuration, flow cell experiments were conducted using a novel circular cell, which was previously designed and fabricated by our research group, to study the deionization performance of the NMO electrodes (Scheme 1).^[61] The circular design was specifically chosen to ensure homogeneous compression of the electrodes, minimizing the distance between them and, consequently, reducing the electric resistance.^[61] The flow cell consisted of two external cases fabricated via 3D printing, 4 Viton gaskets, and two expanded graphite current collectors with specific shapes catted with a silhouette plotter (CAMEO 4). The FDI unit was assembled by utilizing the different NMOs as anode and cathode, and an anion exchange membrane (AEM, Fumapem FAA-3-30) placed between them.

In this rocking-chair, batch-mode configuration, one electrode takes in Na⁺ from the feed solution in one flow channel, while the other releases Na⁺ into the

solution in the opposite channel. At the same time, Cl⁻ migrates from the Na⁺ deficient channel to the Na⁺ enriched channel through the AEM, thus generating desalinated and concentrated effluents simultaneously.^[30] Note that in this cell configuration, an anion-selective membrane was placed between the electrodes, allowing chloride ions to cross from one compartment to the other to compensate for the charge unbalance. Once the desalination process is over, the external current is reversed, leading to the inversion of the process in each channel. By using this configuration, it is possible to achieve continuous deionization in a single-pass process during both steps, charge and discharge, in contrast with the traditional CDI process.

Externally, each side of the case was connected to two Nalgene PVC Tubing (1/16 Wall, Thermo Scientific), from which the electrolyte was pumped through the device with a Masterflex® L/S® peristaltic pump with two heads at 30 mL min⁻¹. For each tank, 40 mL of 0.05 M NaCl solution was chosen as the electrolyte. For the simulated brackish water solution, 25 mL of a solution composed of 0.05 M Na⁺, 0.001 M K⁺, 0.006 M Ca²⁺, and 0.062 M Cl⁻ was employed.

Constant current FDI experiments were performed at different current densities (specified in each experiment), setting a voltage range of ±0.8 V. The variation of the solution conductivity and cell potential was recorded using the flow-type conductivity meter (sensION MM374, HACH) and electrochemical workstation (Biologic SP-150), respectively. The ionic conductivity values obtained from the conductivity meter were smoothed with a Fast Fourier Transformation in Python. The salt removal capacity (SRC, in mg g⁻¹) was calculated using Equation (2):

$$\text{SRC} = \frac{m_{\text{NaCl removed}}}{m_{\text{active material}}} \quad (2)$$

where the amount of NaCl removed (mg NaCl) in one tank is divided by the mass of active material (g NMO) of one electrode when the performance reaches its equilibrium.

The salt removal rate (SRR, in mg g⁻¹ min⁻¹) indicates the kinetics of desalination and was calculated by Equation (3):

Scheme 1. Flow rocking-chair-type full cells (adapted from Fombona-Pascual et al.^[61]).

$$\text{SRR} = \frac{\text{SRC}}{t_{\text{DCH}}} \quad (3)$$

where the mass of salt removed is normalized by total electrode mass and the discharge time (t_{DCH} , min).

The charge efficiency (Λ , %) is defined in Equation (4):

$$\Lambda = \frac{nF100}{Q} \quad (4)$$

and quantifies the ratio of moles of salt removed from the feed (n) to the amount of charge transferred between the electrodes (Q , C) during discharging. F represents the Faraday constant ($96\,485\text{ C mol}^{-1}$).

The volumetric energy consumption (E_V , in kWh m^{-3}) and the molar energy consumption (E_M , in kWh mol^{-1}) are defined in Equations (5) and (6):

$$E_V = \frac{E_c}{V} \quad (5)$$

$$E_M = \frac{E_c}{n} \quad (6)$$

where E_c is the energy needed for one half-cycle (kWh), V is the volume treated in half-cycle (m^3), which corresponds to the volume of one tank (40 mL), and n stands for the moles of salt removed.

The throughput productivity (P , in $\text{L h}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$) is defined in Equation (7):

$$P = \frac{V}{At_{\text{DCH}}} \quad (7)$$

where V is the volume of treated water (L) t_{DCH} is the time of half-cycle (h) and A is the area of the electrode (m^2).

The coulombic efficiency (CE, in %), defined in Equation (8):

$$\text{CE} = \frac{Q_{\text{DCH}}}{Q_{\text{CH}}} \quad (8)$$

quantifies the ratio of electrical charge delivered during the discharge process (Q_{DCH} , mAh g^{-1}) to the charge applied to the cell during charging (Q_{CH} , mAh g^{-1}).

The molar removal ratio (ρ), calculated in Equation (9):

$$\rho = \frac{\frac{i_{\text{initial}} - i_{\text{final}}}{i_{\text{initial}}}}{\frac{j_{\text{initial}} - j_{\text{final}}}{j_{\text{initial}}}} \times 100\% \quad (9)$$

where i_{initial} and i_{final} are the initial and final molar concentrations, respectively, for ion i , and j_{initial} and j_{final} are the initial and final molar concentrations, respectively, for ion j .

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Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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